

Smart city deserves Smart device maintenance: Machine learning is the key

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Abstract. Life in the city has changed on different levels in the past few years. Smart solutions are becoming a part of daily lives of citizens. This leads to an increase in the quality of life in the cities - ordinary cities are slowly transforming into the Smart Cities. On the other hand, in cities there are also devices which the ordinary citizen does not come directly to contact with, but these devices provide significant features like traffic management, oxygen distribution in the subway etc. Any unexpected failure can cause a large economic damage or jeopardize citizens' lives. In order to prevent the failure, these key devices are subject to preventive maintenance which, on the other side, requires a huge amount of human and material resources. Predictive maintenance can be more effective. However, its application is not an easy task. The Smart City requires the deployment of a solution that can independently learn from previous fails and respond to unknown problems. As a solution, we propose an approach based on the utilization of machine learning techniques and recommendation systems.

Keywords: predictive maintenance, artificial intelligence, recommendation system, smart city, machine learning

Introduction

The phenomenon of the Smart City has become an increasingly important part of the lives of citizens in the recent years. Smart City solutions can be beneficial in different areas, for example, they provide an automatic management of electricity, water, and city infrastructure. The effectiveness of these solutions can be increased with utilization of the artificial intelligence (AI) [1]. AI brings useful algorithms for recognition of the images from cameras to increase security, mining of behavioral patterns in citizens lives etc. The use of smart IoT devices in the city's infrastructure is increasing. These smart devices can report their state and various attributes about their performance. Besides them, there is also still a lot of legacy devices which are not able to report any data. For such "unintelligent", but still useful devices, new solutions, which improve capabilities of the city and its staff, are created. However, these solutions require an innovative and intelligent approach. Utilized devices oftentimes require special maintenance and use of lots of documentation about specific maintenance processes and steps, which only experienced personnel understand. In addition, such documentation oftentimes cannot cover all scenarios of device deployment and operation. AI could help. The basic role of artificial intelligence can be perceived as learning, reasoning, and observing. Well set up AI could observe different events of devices, and - based on these events - could learn how to

eliminate possible failures or prevent them from happening. This would improve the condition of managed devices in the city as well as the effectiveness of knowledge and skills sharing among city's employees.

Proposed work

In this article, we suggest an approach that uses various aspects of application of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) to improve the quality of maintenance of various devices in the city administration.

Maintenance and Machine Learning

Promising results of automated device maintenance can be found in many companies of the so-called Industry 4.0. These companies often depend on the proper functioning devices and thus need to avoid their unexpected outages [2]. The same problem must be solved in case of the Smart City in which the security of facilities is essential to prevent massive problems, like electricity/air supply outage. Maintenance approaches, which can monitor equipment conditions for diagnostic and prognostic purposes, can be grouped into three main categories [3]:

- statistical approaches,
- artificial intelligence approaches
- and model-based approaches.

According to [4] model-based approaches need mechanistic knowledge and theory of the equipment to be monitored, and statistical approaches require mathematical background, thus artificial intelligence approaches have been increasingly applied in maintenance applications. Devices maintenance can be divided into the four levels [5]:

- *Run-to-failure (R2F) maintenance*: when repairs or restore actions are performed after the occurrence of a failure.
- *Preventive maintenance (PvM) (or scheduled maintenance)*: when the maintenance is carried out periodically on a planned schedule with the aim of anticipating the process failures.
- *Condition-based maintenance (CBM)*: when the actions on the process are taken after the verification of one or more conditions indicating a degradation of the process or the equipment.
- *Predictive maintenance (PdM) (or statistical-based maintenance)*: similarly, to CBM, maintenance actions are taken only when necessary. However, prediction tools are used to assess when such actions are likely to be required, thus implementing some planning and scheduling schemes. PdM systems can employ ad hoc defined health factors or, in general, statistical inference methods.

At present, mostly preventive maintenance is performed, but from the perspective of efficiency and usage of resources, PdM is the desired style of maintenance. The importance of PdM has recently been growing, as can be seen in the study [4]. A lot of new publications about PdM applied in different areas have been published in last 3 years.

deviations in the history of similar devices can be a clue in searching for possible failure.

Fig. 2. PdM trained with anomaly ML algorithm. Device 1 is like devices 2 and 3. However, in contrast to the history of these similar devices, device 1 shows a large deviation - which can lead to possible outage.

Data modeling and Work in progress

In context of devices maintenance, the Smart City environment consists of three key elements: device, history of device and staff. Device, in additional, can be characterized by constant properties/attributes such as manufacturer, model, power supply, etc. On the other hand, the history of device represents dynamic time series that expands over time. When preprocessing such data, we can use techniques from the field of data mining, such as metrics that could define how similar objects are, and in case of dynamic history (which can reach the dimensions of big data), we could use methods for noise removal, space reduction and sampling. The data prepared in this way then serve as input to the ML algorithms use in PdM.

We are currently at the beginning of industrial and experimental research project. We are working mainly on the processing of input data about devices, employees, and maintenance history - the data preprocessing phase. We considered two options for such data: 1) create your own domain-specific language, or 2) use one of the existing formats. The advantage of the first approach is in the fact that the key modeling concepts can be in the language of end users in the domain. However, the disadvantage lies in the necessity to create an entire ecosystem that supports the validation of data, querying in this data etc. The second option requires adaptation to the used terms in order for them to be expressed using already defined dictionary. On the other side, it provides existing ecosystem of tools. Moreover, the application of such data is not limited to one domain. We chose to use the existing tools.

Environments of the Semantic web provided us with useful tools and languages. Unlike the regular web, on which information is exchanged between the computer and people, the semantic web provides features which enable to transfer data in a form which is understandable by computers – based on ontologies. Ontologies can be used for capturing various kinds of information - they emerged from artificial intelligence and convey the syntax and semantics of concepts and their relationships in a formal, declarative, and computer-understandable way [11]. Authors in [11] used

ontologies and tools from Semantic Web to automatize process of designing system for automatization of buildings. This application strongly reduces designing time and, in the end, reduces the overall costs. Authors in the [12] demonstrated good results in applying of semantic web technologies. They used these techniques in the process of modeling IoT devices in the Web of Things (WoT) environment. Also, according to them, ontologies can capture the various facets in a common, formalized structure as well as the interrelationships between the things to form the domain knowledge of the WoT. In the field of semantic web, Web Ontology Language 2 (OWL2) in combination with the Resource Description Framework (RDF) are considered as good standards. These tools bring implementation independence and, at the same time, enable the information to be represented through a graph structure. This provides universal mathematical model in a form of graphs, which can be used in several areas of ML and AI.

The graph representation provides several algorithms for detection of anomalies [13]. Besides that, graph can empower machine learning projects in several ways along three different directions [14]: Data Management, Data Analysis and Data Visualization. It is also possible to use graph databases to perform complex calculations in a distributed environment. When recommending predictive intervention, it is important to explain to the user why it is required and what kind of failure can occur - graphs help users to focus their attention on specific nodes in a large space.

Conclusion and future works

Approaches from the PdM area, which were the subject of our study, focus mainly on one specific device (photovoltaic panels [15], hard disk drive [16], replacing tungsten filament [6], etc.). Therefore, it is impossible for us to apply those approaches to such a dynamic environment as the Smart City, in which various devices are used. In such environment, it is necessary to describe different devices in a way that would be readable and understandable for computers, and, at the same time, would support ML a PdM for unknown devices. ML and PdM utilization require three steps [17]: Data Preprocessing, Model Learning and Result Interpretation. We followed these steps also in our approach (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. This figure shows overview of our approach for application of predictive maintenance in the Smart City. Required documentation about devices is transformed into graph representation. Then, several methods from domain of machine learning and recommendation systems are used for training of PdM system to detect well known failures or anomalies.

We have access to data related to preventive maintenance performed on devices of different kinds (boilers, diesel aggregators, etc.) from the last 3 years. Most of these data is unstructured and used only for manager reports. We would like to test our approach on such a heterogeneous data set. There are also many other problems to solve, for example, different time granularity of collected data.

Acknowledgement

This article was supported thanks to the generous support under the Operational Program Integrated Infrastructure for the project: "Research Centre for Data Analysis and Protection - II. Stage", Project no. 313021W479, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund.

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